

SSHOC'n Tell Challenge

User Story

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The University Library helps you on your way to Openness

Trying out

SSH
Open
Cluster

SSH TRAINING
DISCOVERY TOOLKIT

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What

I work as head of Research Support at the University Library. My team is currently working on designing trainings on Open Science within the university. Some are more general where Open Science is more a part of a broader theme, like writing a data management plan for PhDs, but we would also like to go into the faculties with a training focus on starting with Open Science. Most researchers have a general feel about what Open Science is but have problems with implementing Open Science in their daily work. We would like to explain that more to them and helping them opening up their research.

Who

For this challenge I am participating alone. At home my team consists of an Open Science Program Manager, a training specialist, two research data stewards and a Open Science Community Manager.

How

I will use the SSH Training Discovery Toolkit to find materials to use in the development of our training.

When

I will present my findings to my team and further work on building our training together with my specialists. We will then test our endproduct with the support office of the faculty of Law, faculty of Humanities, faculty of Social Sciences and the School of Business and Economics. After revising our training based on their feedback, we can then provide the training to the researchers of those faculties.

Try the Toolkit

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